

WORKING OUT OF TECHNOLOGY OF TINCTURE ARTICHOKE

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ABSTRACT

In this experimental part, we obtained conclusions on the improvement of the technological processes of the tincture obtained from the herbal of the prickly artichoke and the creation of an efficient method convenient for production plants.

Theme urgency.

In national and official medicine for a long time it is applied thistle. Artichoke to a liver it is applied in quality hepatoprotektor and is a part of many pharmaceutical preparations. In a chemical compound thistle the spotty includes about 400 valuable components such as macrocells, microcells, vitamins, biogene amins, flavonoids. For the purpose of expansion of the nomenclature of medical products on the basis of medicinal vegetative raw materials we offer tinctures artichoke. Artichoke fruits possess hepato protective action, promote improvement of function of a liver, normalise digestion. The artichoke spotty preventive maintenance protects intact hepatocides and raises their stability to an infection and a various sort to poisonings. The artichoke strengthens formation of bile and accelerates its deducing, normalising thereby processes of digestion and a metabolism.

Research objective. The basic stage of reception galogens preparations is extraction vegetative raw materials. On pharmaceutical manufactures it is spent by periodic methods - maceration, fractional maceration and other methods.

Materials and methods: Object of research are a family artichoke. Numerous factors the big influence on process extraction renders raw materials crushing. Now for many kinds of medicinal raw materials optimum degree of crushing is established. For tincture reception thistle it has been used two methods fractional maceration and percolation. In quality extragent of 80% spirit ethyl has been chosen. Tinctures have received in the ratio 1:5.

Fractional maceration it is spent as follows. The crushed raw materials loaded in maceration a tank and filled in with the first portion extragent and insisted at 24 o'clock, merged the first portion of extraction, raw materials filled in with the second portion extragent and 4 hours insisted. Merged the second portion of extraction. It is process spent two more insisting. The received extraction united, then an incorporated

extract lead up with extragent to the demanded volume. An extract defended (8-10°C) and filtered.

The method percolation includes following stages: soaking raw materials (raw materials swelling), insisting, actually percolation. Crushed raw materials soaking with equal portion (from 50 to 100 % extragent in relation to weight of raw materials), loaded in percolyator and filled in with extragent to a condition of "mirror" and insisted at 24 o'clock. After the expiry of the term spent actually percolation before reception of 5 volume parts of tincture in relation to weight loaded percolyator raw materials.

Results. Clearing of extraction spent upholding at temperature not above 8-10°C before reception of a transparent liquid and a filtration.

Estimation of quality of the received tinctures spent on indicators: the description, relative density, the maintenance of ethanol and the dry rest.

Results of experimental data are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Results indicators of quality of tinctures of a artichoke

The name of an indicator of quality	The tincture of a artichoke received by a method fractional maceration	Tincture a artichoke received by a method percolation
The description	Transparent liquid it is light yellow colour with a greenish shade and bitter taste	Transparent liquid it is light yellow colour with a greenish shade and bitter taste
Relative density	0,860	0,863
The dry rest of %	1,42	1,48
The maintenance of ethanol, %	70,00	70,60

Apparently from the given tables of tincture a artichoke received by methods fractional maceration and percolation corresponded to requirements of the standard documentation.

CONCLUSIONS

It is offered the fastest and economic methods of reception of tincture from artichoke seeds. Optimum conditions extraction are picked up: extragent- 80 % ethyl spirit, a parity of raw materials and extragent 1:5. The estimation of quality of the received tinctures according to requirements standard documentation on indicators the description, relative density, the dry rest and the ethanol maintenance is spent. Both offered ways have allowed to receive tinctures corresponding on quality of the standard documentation.

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